

From : J ■■■ F ■■■ K ■■■ M ■■■

To : The Clerk to the Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs

Subject : Memorandum on the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill

Date: 6th October 2021

1.0 Introduction:

Joseph Felix Kwesi Mensah wishes to respond to the request put out by the Parliament of Ghana on 15th September 2021 asking for written Memoranda on 3 bills before Parliament. We intend to focus on the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill.

2.0 Core Issues:

The position of Joseph Felix Kwesi Mensah on the subject of the LGBTQIA + community and substantively the PPSHRGFV bill is as follows:

2.1. Regarding the matter of Lesbian, Gay and Bisexual practices, it is our opinion in line with biblical standards that gender was created as 'binary' – God created male and female from the beginning (Gen. 1:26,27; Deut. 22:5). Gender is divine (1 Cor. 11:2,3-16), and is predestined and assigned before birth (Jer.1:5; Lk.1:15; Gal.1:15; Eph.1:3,4; 2:10). This is what Jesus Christ and His apostles believed (Matt.19:4-11; Mk.10:5-9; Col.1:15,16; 1 Cor.6:16; Eph.5:31).

Moreover, it is our opinion that marriage as defined by Christianity is a lifelong covenant between man and woman, that enables procreation and a protective home for the nurture of children (Heb.13:4; Gen.2:18,24; Eph.5:22-33; Col.3:19-21; 1 Pet.3:1-7). It typifies the union of Christ and the Church, and is a divine institution (Eph.5:22-33; 2 Cor.11:3).

Again, the Christian Bible is clear on God's hatred of such practices, and the consequences that fall upon any individual or group that practices them, both in the Old Testament (Lev.18:22; 20:13; Gen. 19; Judges 7; Judges 19-21) and the New Testament (1 Cor.6:9; Rom.1:27; 1 Tim.1:10). The commands of God against sexual lust apply to all, no matter what self-constructed ideas of sexual orientation are held to (1 Cor.7:1-2; 1 Thess.4:4-7; Heb.13:4).

We therefore plead that this bill be passed in order to save our land from the wrath of God.

2.2. We argue also that just as natural events such as sunrise and sunset, floods, hurricanes, etc. cannot be legislated by human governments because they did not create these systems and events, so also the marriage relationship was instituted by God and not man. We therefore do not have the right to legislate marriage, but must accept it as God prescribed – between one man and one woman.

2.3. We also support the passing of this bill for the sake of our future as a nation and society as a whole. By allowing individuals to define for themselves their gender and live as they feel they are "wired" to, it

